

TETHERED SPINAL CORD IN THE GENESIS OF NEUROLOGICAL DISORDERS IN CHILDREN WITH OSTEONEUROLOGIC DYSPLASIA

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Abstract. *The purpose of the study is to establish the frequency of individual anatomical variants, their clinical and neurological manifestations; to evaluate the effectiveness of complex treatment of children with fixed spinal cord syndrome with osteoneural abnormalities of the spine and spinal cord. The work is based on the analysis of the diagnosis and treatment results of 321 patients: 156 (48.6%) boys and 165 (51.4%) girls aged one day to 18 years with latent spinal dysraphism of various forms in combination with other types of spinal malformations. According to the results of studies among patients with Spina bifida aperta, 106 (48.4%) out of 219 patients and out of 102 patients with Spina bifida occulta, 7 (6.9%) had a "fixed spinal cord". The most common causes of SPSM are latent spinal dysraphism of congenital genesis (lipomyelocele, diastatomyelia, syringomyelia, hydromyelia) and the phenomena of the syndrome of secondary fixation of the spinal cord that occur after surgery.*

Keywords: *fixed spinal cord, spinal dysraphism, children.*

The term "fixed spinal cord" (tethered spinal cord) was introduced by H.J. Hoffmann et al. in 1976. During normal fetal development in the third month, the spinal cord occupies the entire length of the spinal canal. In the following months, the spine grows faster than the spinal cord, which results in the spinal cord ending at the level of the third lumbar vertebra at birth. By the age of 12–18 months, it reaches the lower edge of the first lumbar vertebra (LI) or the upper edge of the second lumbar vertebra (LII). If the spinal cord cone and epiconus are located below this level and accompanied by corresponding clinical symptoms, it is considered a manifestation of the pathological condition known as "fixed spinal cord syndrome" [1, 6, 7, 10].

The term "tethered cord syndrome" (fixed spinal cord syndrome) was proposed by S. Yamada et al. in 1981. This condition arises due to the tension and restricted mobility of the spinal cord, caused by its fixation in the lumbosacral region. This fixation leads to metabolic impairments and disruptions in the physiological activities of the caudal neuronal formations [28].

Fixed spinal cord syndrome combines a group of diseases of congenital or acquired origin with a common pathogenic mechanism, caused by tension in the organ due to the fixation of its caudal part. Dysplasia of the osteo-neural development of the spinal cord and spinal column manifests clinically through a combination of motor, sensory, trophic, and pelvic dysfunctions, as well as deformities in the lower extremities and internal organ dysfunctions.

From the modern perspective, fixed spinal cord syndrome includes all cases of spinal dysraphism, acquired post-traumatic, post-infectious, and other conditions that involve fixation and tension of the caudal spinal cord. Congenital causes include spinal dysraphism, where intrauterine fixation of the spinal cord is a common feature. The most frequent congenital causes are lumbosacral lipomas (lipomyelomeningocele, terminal thread lipomas, terminal cone lipomas), dermal sinus tracts, diastatomyelia, and dorsal fixation cords in meningocele [4]. In acquired

cases, the source of fixation is scar tissue inside the dural sac, often occurring after surgical correction of spinal dysraphism, known as "secondary spinal cord fixation syndrome" (SVFSM). Every third child who undergoes correction for myelomeningocele requires another surgery to "release the spinal cord" due to SVFSM development [9].

Objective: To determine the frequency of individual anatomical variants and their clinical and neurological manifestations, as well as evaluate the effectiveness of complex treatments for children with fixed spinal cord syndrome and osteoneural spinal cord anomalies based on clinical data.

Materials and Methods: The study is based on an analysis of diagnostics and treatment results for 321 patients (156 boys – 48.6%, 165 girls – 51.4%) aged from one day to 18 years with latent spinal dysraphism of various forms, combined with other types of spinal malformations, treated in the Department of Elective Surgery at Tashkent City Children’s Hospital No. 2 and the Department of Pediatric Neurosurgery at the Scientific Center of Neurosurgery of the Ministry of Health of Uzbekistan from 2018–2022.

Patients were divided into two groups. The first (comparison) group consisted of 77 patients (24%) observed from 2011–2013. The second (main) group consisted of 244 patients (76%) observed from 2018–2022. Various types of spinal pathology were identified based on functional and instrumental studies. Spina bifida aperta was found in 219 patients (68.2%) and spina bifida occulta in 102 patients (31.8%), with associated anorectal anomalies in 51 patients (50%), urogenital anomalies in 13 patients (12.75%), colon pathology in 30 patients (29.41%), and isolated forms in 8 patients (7.84%).

Patients underwent standard neurological examinations, as well as consultations with pediatricians and other specialized physicians. Clinical and laboratory methods were used, along with imaging methods (ultrasound, MSCT, MRI), and electromyography (EMG) for the lower extremity muscles. To assess the anatomical and functional states of the colon and urogenital system, targeted ultrasound, irrigography, and intravenous urography were performed using digital X-ray equipment or MSCT.

Results and Discussion: Among patients with spina bifida aperta, 106 (48.4%) of 219 patients and 7 (6.9%) of 102 patients with spina bifida occulta had "fixed spinal cord." The diagnostic criterion was characteristic changes revealed by imaging methods. Of 219 patients with a history of surgery for cystic forms of spinal dysraphism, fixed spinal cord was detected in 106, with the following morphological forms: myelomeningoradiculocele in 33 cases (29.2%), lipomyelomeningocele in 21 cases (18.6%), and meningo-radiculocele in 52 cases (46%). Of 94 patients operated on for anorectal and urogenital abnormalities combined with latent spinal dysraphism, fixed spinal cord syndrome was identified in 7 cases (7.4%).

Table 1

Neurological status of patients with fixed spinal cord (n=106)

Disorder Type	Pathology Type			Total
	Myelomeningo- radiculocele N= 30/3	Meningo- radiculocele n=49/3	Lipomyelomeningo- radiculocele n=18/3	97/9
Lower flaccid paresis (monoparesis, paraparesis)	23(31,1%) / 2(25%)	43(58,1%) / 3(37,5%)	8(10,8%) / 3(37,5%)	74(76,3%) / 8(88,9%)

Lower spastic paresis (monoparesis, paraparesis)	7(41,2%) / 1(100%)	4(23,5%) / -	6(35,3%) / -	17(17,5%) / 1(11,1%)
Reduced sensitivity	21(33,3%) / 3(33,33%)	32(50,8%) / 3(33,33%)	10(15,9%) / 3(33,34%)	63(64,9%) / 9(100%)
Trophic disorders	9(26,5%) / 3(33,33%)	19(55,9%) / 3(33,33%)	6(17,6%) / 3(33,34%)	34(35%) / 9(100%)
Pain syndrome	2(18,2%) / 2(40%)	4(36,4%) / 2(40%)	5(45,5%) / 1(20%)	11(11,3%) / 5(55,6%)
Pelvic organ dysfunction	30(31,6%) / 3(33,33%)	47(49,5%) / 3(33,33%)	18(18,9%) / 3(33,34%)	95(97,9%) / 9(100%)
Combination of neurological deficits	30(37,5%) / 3(33,33%)	32(40%) / 3(33,33%)	18(22,5%) / 3(33,34%)	80(82.3.3%) / 9(100%)
No pathological changes	-/-5	5(71,4%) / -2	2(28,6%) / -7	7(6,6,6%) / -

Note: The numerator represents the main group and the denominator represents the comparison group.

Motor disorders, peripheral or mixed types of paresis of the lower extremities up to plegia were observed in 100 (94.3%) patients. According to the parents, the child was noted to be restless and irritable when moving. Sensitivity disorders in 72 (67.9%) patients were represented by hyposthesia and anesthesia of the lower extremities and perineal-gluteal region. In 16 (15.1%) children of older age groups, pain (headache, in the lumbar region and lower extremities) was noted. As a rule, pain was not always associated with SPSM. However, an increase in pain when checking for symptoms of nerve trunk tension with progressive asymmetric muscle dystonia in the lower extremities, segmental or radicular sensory disorders, and pelvic organ dysfunctions indicates that the pain syndrome is involved in disorders of fixation of the thermal part of the spinal cord. Pelvic organ dysfunction in 104 (98%) patients, manifested by disorders of urodynamics, the act of defecation alone or in combination, was a frequent clinical occurrence of SPSM. Trophic disorders in the form of symmetrical or asymmetrical atrophy of the extremities, trophic deformities, mainly in the distal parts of the lower extremities, were observed in 43 (40.5%) patients. Trophic ulcers of various severity were observed in 12 of them. 89 (85.6%) out of 106 patients had a combination of two or more neurological disorders in complex, severe, and extensive SPS lesions. Spinal deformities were observed in 39 (36.8%) patients with myelodysplasia with latent forms of spinal dystrophism and fixed spinal cord (FSM). Formed scoliosis or a combination of scoliosis and lordosis can be considered a factor that aggravates the disproportion of osteoneural development of the spinal cord and spinal column and the severity of neurological deficits, even if the caudal spinal cord is located in areas relative to the vertebral bodies.

Children who underwent surgery for spinal malformations, anorectal, urogenital abnormalities, and colon pathology received corrective treatment with the participation of a pediatric orthopedist, urologist, and surgeon. The complex of treatment included physiotherapy procedures (massage, physical therapy, UHF, laser therapy, FTL) and medications (vascular,

nootropic, vitamins gr. C) every 4-6 months, for two years. The dynamics of neurological disorders after operations and 4-5-fold complex therapy was different in intensity (Table. 2).

Table 2

Dynamics of the severity of neurological disorders after surgical treatment in children with SPSM (n=106)

Type of disorder	Number of cases	Dynamics at treatment stages					
		Positive		Without dynamics		Negative	
		Abs.	%	Abs.	%	Abs.	%
Motor	Skills 100 (94,3%)	19	19%	73	73%	8	8%
Sensitive	ones 72 (67,9%)	9	12,5%	61	84,7%	2	2,8%
Pain syndrome	16 (15,1%)	12	75%	4	25%	--	-
Pelvic dysfunctions	104 (98%)	35	33,7%	63	60,6%	8	7,7%
Trophic	43 (40,5%)	9	20,9%	31	72,1%	3	7%
Combined failures	89 (85,6%)	10	11,2%	71	79,8%	8	9%
No violations	7(6,6%)	-	-	-	-	-	-

As can be seen from Table 3, 19 patients showed positive dynamics with an increase in muscle strength in the " affected " limbs, muscle mass volume, and improvement in muscle tone. 8 patients had negative dynamics. In 73% of cases, motor disorders remained without dynamics. Positive dynamics of sensitive disorders were observed in 9 (12.5%) children, 61 (84.7%) children remained without dynamics), and 2 (2.8%) children had worsened sensitive disorders. After surgical treatment, regression of the pain syndrome was noted in 12 (75%). 4 (25%) patients complained of periodic pain in the surgical area and lower extremities. Normalization or partial improvement of bladder and rectal function was observed in 35 (33.7%) patients. In 63 (60.6%) patients, pelvic disorders remained without dynamics, and 8 (7.7%) patients had a negative dynamic. Different dynamics of neurological disorders maybe associated with inadequate elimination of combined latent spinal dysraphism. In 37 (34.9%) cases, the development of SPSM can be associated with secondary fixation of spinal cord elements to adjacent tissues in the surgical area. The absence of positive and development of negative dynamics in the form of increased pain in the back and lower extremities, progressive sensory and motor disorders; preservation of pronounced pelvic organ dysfunctions indicates the involvement of residual neurosurgical components of SPSM phenomena and requires prompt correction to eliminate the causes of pathological fixation of the spinal cord.

The clinical significance of latent spinal dysraphism noteworthy in 102 (31.8%) patients with spina bifida occulta: in association with anorectal pathologies, it was detected in 51 (50 %); urogenital pathologies - in 13 (12.75%); with colon pathology - in 30 (29.41%) patients who underwent surgery by nature patients with established pathology and in 8 (7.84%) - in an isolated form, observed in a pediatric surgery clinic. According to the results of preoperative studies, the frequency of latent spinal dysraphism was different and significantly differed in the nature of the detected disorders (Table3).

According to radiological diagnostic methods, in 7 (10.9%) patients of this group, changes in the spinal column were manifested by scoliosis. Localization of the terminal thread in the spinal

cord structure was detected on MSCT in 6 cases. 4 (6.25%) patients had tethering syndrome, 2 (3.13%) had intradural lipoma. Of the 30 children with coloproctological abnormalities, 2 (6.7%) had postural disorder, 2 (6.7%) had sacral malformations, and 1 had vertebral body abnormalities localized in the lumbosacral region. Tethering syndrome was diagnosed in 1 (3.3%) patient.

Table 3

Combined lumbosacral dysraphism in anorectal, urogenital, and coloproctological anomalies in children (n = 94)

Type of latent spinal dysraphism	dysraphism Number of detected cases n=94	With anorectal and urogenital anomalies n=64		With colon anomalies n=30 Qty	
		nab.	%	qty nab	%
No violations detected	-	-		-	
Postural disorders (scoliosis, kyphosis, lordosis)	9 (9,57%)	7	10,9%	2	6,7%
Non-sealing of the shackles:					
a) one vertebra	55 (58,5%)	9	14,1%	-8	-
b) two		15	23,4%	8	26,7%
c) more than two		9	14,1%	14-2	46,6%
Anomaly of the vertebral bodies	5 (5,32%)	4	6,25%	1	3,3%
Sacral malformation (agenesis, dysgenesis, deviation)	7(7.44%)	5	7.81	2	6.7%
Coccyx abnormalities	7(7.44%)	7	10.9%	-	
Lipoma	2(2.127%)	2	3.13%	-	
Tetring syndrome	5 (5.32%)	4	6,25%	1	3,3%
Combining individual forms	8(8.51%)	6	9,37%	2	6,7%
Total	98	68		30	

Clinical manifestations in these patients are characterized by the prevalence of one of the neurological disorders or a different combination of motor, sensory, trophic and pelvic disorders, osteoarticular deformities of the lower extremities and dysfunctions of internal organs.

Conclusions.

In the genesis of residual and progressive neurological disorders in children after operations for spinal deformities, the leading place is occupied by the phenomena of the "fixed spinal cord" syndrome in the form of pronounced congenital pathology before surgery or an adhesive process, associated with surgical intervention.

The most common cause of SPSM is latent spinal dysraphism of congenital origin (lipomyelocele, diastatomyelia, syringomyelia, hydromyelia) and secondary spinal cord fixation syndrome phenomena, that occur after surgery.

After surgery, patients need dynamic neurological monitoring, comprehensive treatment with the participation of specialists.

Patients with SPSM with progressive negative dynamics on the background of conservative therapy need surgical treatment to eliminate the phenomena of spinal cord fixation.

REFERENCES

1. Al Absi Esmat, Voronov V. G., Mazur V. G., Kutumov E. B., Yalfimov A. N. "Fixed spinal cord" syndrome in caudal spinal dysraphy. // Siberian Medical Journal .- 2007, No. 3, pp. 10-13.
2. Voronov V. G., Syrchin E. F., Zyabrov A. A., Ivanov A. A., Potemkina E. G., Pershin V. A. Fixed spinal cord syndrome: current concepts of etiology and pathogenesis, clinical picture, diagnosis and treatment (review of scientific publications). // Scientific and practical journal "Neurology and neurosurgery of children".- 2011. - No. 2. - p. 53-61.
3. Gaiduk Yu. V., Sharina I. E. Features of disorders of the nervous system in congenital lesions of the musculoskeletal system and malformations of the spinal cord. // Scientific and practical journal "Clinical and Laboratory Consultation".- 2008. - p. 35-40.
4. Demyanenko V. A., Kabanyan A. B., Baidakov A. P., Ermakov S. V., Firsov A. L. Diagnostics and treatment tactics of types of latent spinal dysraphism (spina bifida occulta): dorsal dermal sinus, fixed spinal cord syndrome. // Кубанский Scientific Medical Bulletin.- 2012. - №6 (135). - P. 85-87.
5. Kushel Yu. V., Zemlyansky M. Yu. Syndrome of "secondary fixation of the spinal cord" after correction of various forms of spinal dysraphism in children. // NEUROSURGERY.- 2010. - No. 2. - pp. 41-46.
6. Rudakova A.V., Larionov S. N., Sorokovikov V. A., Gruzin P. G., Byankin V. F. Some features of diagnosis and treatment of osteoneural dysplasia - "fixed spinal cord" // BULLETIN ВЧШ СО РАМН of the Supreme Scientific Research Center of the Siberian Branch of the Russian Academy of Medical Sciences.- 2010.- № 5 (75).- P. 119-120.
7. Rudakova A.V., Larionov S. N. Features of diagnosis and treatment of spinal malformations in childhood. // Bulletin ВЧШ СО of the Supreme Scientific Research Center of the Siberian Branch of the Russian Academy of Medical Sciences.- 2012.- № 4 (86).- 2. - P. 110-113.
8. Syr'chin E. F. Syndrome of "fixed spinal cord" in children with caudal spine and spinal cord dysraphy. // Abstract дисс. of Ph. D. - dissertation-Perm.- 2005.- p. 12-20.
9. Jamie D Olesen , Darcie A Kiddoo, Peter D Metcalfe The association between urinary continence and quality of life in paediatric patients with spina bifida and tethered cord. // Paediatr Child Health.- 2013.- Vol.18 No 7. P.32-35.
10. Kang J.K., Yoon K.J., Ha S.S. et al. Surgical management and outcome of tethered cord syndrome in school aged children, adolescents, and young adults // J. Korean. Neurosurg. Soc. — 2009. — Vol. 46. — P. 468–471.